

HEREDITARY

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Deliverable 6.5

Citizen science and terminology: Methodology

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report explores the growing importance of citizen science and the critical need for clear, accessible communication of scientific concepts to non-experts. As citizen involvement in research increases, so does the need to ensure that terminology is not a barrier to participation.

One key challenge is the development and use of simplified definitions that are understandable to a general audience without compromising scientific accuracy. To address this, the report proposes a structured methodology for the comprehension-based appraisal of definitions by non-experts. This collaborative yet controlled process enables the evaluation of whether simplified terms truly support inclusive engagement.

Central to this approach is the role of the terminologist, who acts as a bridge between domain experts and the public. Terminologists ensure conceptual accuracy, consistency, and clarity across definitions, adapting terminology to be both scientifically valid and accessible to non-specialist audiences. Their expertise is essential in developing terminology that meets the dual goals of precision and public understanding.

Building on insights from Freitag and Pfeffer (2013), who emphasize the value of citizen perspectives, this report argues for a participatory, expert-guided approach to terminology validation. By integrating terminologists into the co-design of definitions and incorporating feedback from non-expert users, the process supports more transparent, inclusive, and effective communication in citizen science projects across Europe.

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AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
Rute Costa	UNL
Margarida Ramos	UNL
Matilde Canelas	UNL
Ana Mouro	UNL
Chiara Lovati	Observa
Giuseppe Pellegrini	Observa
Federica Vezzani	UNIPD
Vanessa Bonato	UNIPD
Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio	UNIPD
Carlos Iglesias Losada (Internal reviewer)	FEUGA
Amalia Hafner Táboas (Internal reviewer)	FEUGA
Anna Romanovych (Contributor)	UNIPD

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Contents

1	Introduction.....	11
2	Citizen Science	13
2.1	Introduction to Citizen Science: Definition and Evolution.....	13
2.2	Citizen Science: A Two-Way Approach	13
2.3	Conclusion: Future Directions in Citizen Science	14
3	Understanding Communication and Terminology Use in Health Settings	15
3.1	What is Communication?	15
3.2	What is the Impact of “Good” Terminology in the Communication Process? 15	
3.3	Specialized VS Simplified Definitions	16
3.4	Validation of Terminology Process	17
4	Stakeholders’ Typology	18
4.1	Experts.....	18
4.2	Non-Experts	18
5	Workflow Description.....	19
6	Methodology Used for the Design of the Survey	23
6.1	Introduction	23
6.2	Survey Structure	23
6.3	Question Types and Justification	23
6.4	Sections Overview	24
6.5	Ethical Considerations	24
6.6	Limitations.....	25
6.7	Conclusion	25
7	Methodology Used for the Design of the Questionnaire Script.....	26
7.1	Introduction	26
7.2	Objectives	26
7.3	Selection of Corpora for Terminological Data	26
7.3.1	Selection of Terms and Definitions.....	26
7.3.2	Overview of Corpora and Creation of a Corpus of Semi-Specialized texts 27	
7.4	Participant Assignment	29
7.5	Questionnaire Script	29
7.6	Data Analysis	30
7.6.1	Quantitative Analysis.....	30
7.6.2	Qualitative Analysis.....	31
7.7	Practical Relevance and Future Application	31

8	Preparing Stakeholders Before Answering the Questionnaire	32
8.1	Introduction	32
8.2	Adapting Communication to Support Informed Participation	32
8.3	Pilot Testing and Feedback Loops	32
8.4	Continuous Support and Follow-Up	32
9	Future Work	33
10	Conclusions	34
	References	35
	Annexes	41

List of Tables

Table 1	Creating a Self-Generated Identification Code (SGIC)	25
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List of Figures

Figure 1	Workflow description	22
----------	----------------------	----

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full extension
app	Application
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
ERC	Research Ethics Review Committee
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
HAS	Haute Autorité de Santé
HLS-EU	European Health Literacy Survey
HLS-EU-Q	European Health Literacy Survey Questionnaire
HSL	Health Social Lab
ICPSR	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research
IQWiG	Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlichkeit im Gesundheitswesen
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
KRC	Knowledge-rich context
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MSD	Merck Sharp & Dohme
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NLM	National Library of Medicine
OED	Oxford English Dictionary
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SGIC	Self-generated identification codes
TC	Technical committee
TR	Terminological resource
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WHO	World Health Organization

1 Introduction

Citizen Science has emerged as a dynamic and evolving field that bridges the gap between scientific research and public participation. By involving non-expert volunteers in the process of scientific inquiry, Citizen Science promotes inclusive knowledge production, fosters public engagement with science, and supports data collection on a scale often unattainable by professional researchers alone. This document aims to explore the multifaceted nature of Citizen Science, its stakeholders, communication challenges, and methodologies designed to enhance participant involvement and the clarity of scientific terminology.

The first part of this report provides a comprehensive overview of Citizen Science, beginning with its definition and historical evolution. It then examines the two-way relationship between experts and non-experts, highlighting how collaborative efforts can generate mutual benefits.

Understanding the roles and perspectives of the different stakeholders involved is crucial. The typology of participants distinguishes between experts, who contribute specialized knowledge, and non-experts, who offer valuable observations and grassroots insights. Effective communication between these groups is paramount for successful collaboration. Therefore, the report delves into communication aspects and the significance of using appropriate terminology. It discusses the balance between specialized definitions and simplified definitions to ensure clear, accessible, and meaningful exchanges.

Subsequent sections outline the methodological framework employed in the study, including survey and questionnaire design, ethical considerations, and limitations. The methodology also covers the selection and creation of textual corpora used for term extraction and the development of definitions that accommodate both expert and lay audiences. Validation processes and iterative revalidation ensure the reliability and usability of these definitions in real-world Citizen Science settings.

The methodology employed in this report plays a crucial role in underpinning the success of citizen science initiatives. It serves as a foundational element for fostering effective communication between experts and non-experts. Specifically, the design and implementation of the survey and questionnaire emerge as valuable tools for exploring citizens' knowledge and perceptions of medical terminology. In this context, the methodology is not just a procedural detail but a strategic approach to capturing public understanding and attitudes. Thus, the methodology becomes essential for ensuring that citizen perspectives are accurately and meaningfully integrated into the broader project objectives.

Finally, the document addresses future work aimed at further refining communication strategies and enhancing participant engagement. By providing a structured approach to terminology and stakeholder interaction, this report contributes to the ongoing development of Citizen Science as an inclusive and impactful approach to research.

This report provides insights into future directions, emphasizing the growing importance of Citizen Science in addressing societal challenges.

In addition to the introduction, future work, conclusions, and annexes, the document is organized into eight main sections. Section 2 outlines our understanding of citizen

science. Section 3 discusses the role of terminology science in specialized communication, detailing our approach to both specialized and simplified definitions and underscoring the importance of a robust validation process. Section 4 identifies the types of stakeholders we aim to involve during the project's implementation phase, which is set to begin in the next steps starting September 2025. Section 5 describes the validation workflow for specialized and simplified definitions, broken down into several steps and corresponding tasks. Section 6 introduces the methodology for designing the survey. Section 7 resents the approach for drafting the questionnaire script. Finally, Section 8 outlines how stakeholders should be prepared before responding to the questionnaires.

We consider this work a key contribution to the success of citizen science initiatives, providing an essential foundation for fostering effective communication between experts and non-experts.

2 Citizen Science

2.1 Introduction to Citizen Science: Definition and Evolution

First noted in 1989 in the MIT Technology Review on community-based laboratories (OED, 2025), the term Citizen Science has become subject of debate among academics, being recognized in 2014 by the Oxford English Dictionary as "scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions" (Davis et al., 2023). There are many different approaches when it comes to defining Citizen Science, but there is a common trait underlying all approaches: Citizen Science consists of a community type of science. It involves citizens at various stages of the scientific research process (EU, 2025) - from defining the problem to analyzing data - and results in greater local involvement, easier access to knowledge and higher inclusivity. The growth of Citizen Science has been undeniable¹.

2.2 Citizen Science: A Two-Way Approach

Recognizing Citizen Science's flexible and evolving nature, the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) has established ten guiding principles that can promote good practice in this field:

1. Citizens must always be involved (whether as contributors, collaborators, or project leaders).
2. A research question must be addressed, and actions must always be informed.
3. Both professional scientists and citizen scientists must benefit from their participation (e.g. publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment or social benefits).
4. Citizen scientists' participation should be encouraged at various stages of the scientific process.
5. Regular feedback should be provided to citizen scientists.
6. Greater public engagement and democratization of science must be ensured.
7. Project data and metadata must be published in an open-access format.
8. Citizen scientists should be acknowledged in project results and publications.
9. Programs must be evaluated considering their scientific output, data quality, participants' experience, and societal or policy impact.
10. Legal and ethical issues related to copyright, intellectual property, data sharing, confidentiality, attribution, and environmental impact must be considered.

(Haklay et al. 2020)

Freitag and Pfeffer (2013) highlight the additional benefits of citizen science, as it provides access to citizens' individual knowledge and perspectives. This fosters crucial insights and diverse outcomes beyond traditional scientific approaches (p. 1). The engagement of citizen scientists contributes to better understanding, more tailored solutions and stronger connections between science and everyday life. (Freitag & Pfeffer, 2013, p. 1).

¹ A Google Scholar search for this term reveals that approximately 12,100 articles have been published since the beginning of 2025.

The wide range of benefits offered by Citizen Science has been broadly recognized. However, as Balázs et al. (2021) draw attention to, “data quality issues are the Achilles heel of citizen science projects” (p. 141), highlighting the need to improve the quality of Citizen Science data. Downs et al. (2021) also address this issue, recommending that future research defines a systematic approach that guarantees Citizen Science data quality and allows it to be broadly reused (pp. 4-5). That is why, in this report, we propose a method (see Section 5) that incorporates data validation through a collaborative yet controlled approach.

Despite the call for inclusion, citizen scientists are often reduced to “a silent means to an end” (Hall et al., 2024, p. 19), as they are often engaged in the process of data collection, but not in later stages, such as data analysis. The fact that most peer-reviewed articles involving citizen science provide limited or no investigation into motivations of participants also leads to a practical concern: ethical questions can arise and access to valuable information about social and ecological systems may be hampered (Hall et al., 2024, pp. 319-320). Incorporating feedback from citizen scientists and fostering continuous communication, based on the sharing of knowledge, goals, and outcomes, not only promotes sustained citizen involvement over time, but also makes science more responsive to community needs. This approach develops more meaningful research, strengthens scientific methodology, and increases the validity of citizen science projects (Hall et al., 2024, p. 320; Davis et al., 2023, p. 2).

2.3 Conclusion: Future Directions in Citizen Science

Given the growing recognition and support for citizen science in Europe, a strategic approach should be defined. According to Vohland et al. (2021, pp. 49–50) and Liu et al. (2021, pp. 439; 456), this approach should be built upon the following pillars:

- a. Promoting good practice in project development - Disseminating Citizen Science initiatives through effective networking, translation and implementation of more structured methodologies
- b. Engaging with strategic partners - Creating partnerships can support local initiatives and integrate the top-down and bottom-up dimensions of citizen science
- c. Integrating citizen science into scientific research - Aligning citizen science with European policy priorities, ensuring training for specific stakeholder groups and facilitating knowledge transfer and innovation.
- d. Developing adequate infrastructures - This requires creating platforms with easy access to data, practical examples, toolkits and scientific results that can be useful to different stakeholders (including non-professional citizens, institutions or public media).
- e. Maintaining openness and flexibility - These two approaches are crucial to ensuring the adaptability to the evolving needs of Citizen Science communities.

Ultimately, the future development of citizen science will depend on the ability to create collaborative platforms that facilitate teamwork among all stakeholders, promote the dissemination of open data and support the development of coherent theoretical frameworks and methodological standards.

3 Understanding Communication and Terminology Use in Health Settings

3.1 What is Communication?

Communication is a process through which individuals interactively “create, sustain, and modify systems of meaning” (Conrad & Poole, 2012).

Communication between experts and non-experts in clinical contexts extends beyond conveying technical information. Street Jr. et al. (2009, pp. 297-299) proposed pathways through which clinician-patient communication contributes to improved health outcomes. According to the authors, effective communication between these parties indirectly enhances patient health by promoting trust in practitioners, increasing satisfaction with the care provided, and enhancing patient knowledge. It strengthens patients’ ability to assess their health status and potential treatment options and encourages more informed decision-making. In conclusion, it promotes patient agency, positively contributing to greater self-management skills and adherence to therapeutic recommendations while enhancing therapeutic alliances and activating social support.

In interactions between experts and non-experts, communication is not a neutral process but one embedded within a broader context of relational dynamics. For instance, relational dominance may exist between healthcare providers and non-experts, and message incongruences can arise when the parties lack a shared understanding. As Littlejohn & Foss (2009) observed, research has shown that too often in healthcare situations, consumers and providers do not directly answer the questions posed to them or respond congruently to topics raised during conversations. Sometimes, healthcare participants have different agendas for the conversation, may not be ready to disclose personal information that is requested, or may struggle to understand comments or articulate responses effectively.

3.2 What is the Impact of “Good” Terminology in the Communication Process?

The impact of terminology in communication stems from its dual role (Costa, 2013). At the linguistic level, terminology serves as a vehicle for the transmission of specialized knowledge and meaning. At the conceptual level, terms designate concepts corresponding to a unique combination of characteristics (ISO 1087:2019). Clearly defined concepts thus reinforce conceptual stability and reduce discourse ambiguity by fostering a shared understanding of terms and concepts among the interlocutors.

In specialized domains, where terminological ambiguity can lead to misunderstandings among experts, terminological work provides a framework for organizing knowledge by structuring the domain’s conceptual and linguistic system, which facilitates effective communication. In clinical contexts, for instance, the harmonization of terms designating concepts such as symptoms, diagnoses, and treatment procedures, as well as their definition, establishes a stable relationship between a concept and its associated term, ensuring clarity and preventing miscommunication. Additionally, in interdisciplinary settings where communication occurs between professionals from different fields of expertise, terminology harmonization allows for the alignment of distinct conceptual frameworks.

In patient-oriented contexts where communication occurs among individuals with diverse backgrounds, the use of appropriate terminology becomes particularly crucial. Inconsistencies heighten the risk of miscommunication for patients and non-experts, for whom medical terminology is often complex due to its specificity (Wermuth & Verplaetse, 2019).

Hence, the use of adequate and precise terminology – derived from denominative harmonization and clear definitions – minimizes ambiguity in healthcare communication, fostering greater precision in the exchange of information among experts, patients, and non-experts.

3.3 Specialized VS Simplified Definitions

According to ISO 1087:2019, a definition is a “representation of a concept by an expression that describes it and differentiates it from related concepts.” This means that a definition is a precise linguistic tool used to represent the concept within a specific domain, while also making clear how it differs from other similar concepts as part of a concept system. The ISO standard emphasizes that definitions must be systematic and concept-oriented, which is essential for building coherent and interoperable terminologies across disciplines and languages.

In terminology work, especially in technical and scientific fields, definitions serve a vital function: they ensure that communication is clear, consistent, and unambiguous. A well-formed definition does more than simply describe what something is. It sets boundaries around the concept by identifying its essential characteristics and distinguishing it from related concepts. This is what sets a definition apart from a general explanation or description².

Different types of definitions are used to address different audiences within the same domain. Specialized definitions are intended for experts and use precise, technical language, whereas simplified definitions aim to make concepts accessible to non-experts through clearer and more general wording.

ISO TC 37 704 (2022) states that when writing a definition, the target audience has to be taken into account. ISO 704 (2022, p. 33) identifies three types of different audiences:

- i. Experts in the domain or subject in question, already familiar with the relevant conceptualization patterns and who can be familiar with the designations.
- ii. Experts from other domains or non-experts who can be familiar with the designations and the concepts.
- iii. Non-experts who are unfamiliar with both the designations and the concepts of the domain or subject.

We consider that audience type (i) consists of experts, type (ii) of informed users, and type (iii) of non-experts. Types (i) and (ii) are the target audiences for specialized definitions, whose purpose is to convey the exact meaning of a concept within a particular field. In contrast, non-experts (type iii) require definitions that make the concept accessible to a general audience. This is known as a simplified definition. Simplified

² For the purpose of this report, we will not go into the details of the differences between “simplified definition”, “explanation” and “description”. This will be tackled as future work.

definitions often use plain language techniques, minimize or clarify domain-specific terms, and convey complex concepts in an accessible way.

3.4 Validation of Terminology Process

Clear and validated terminology is essential for effective communication within a multilingual and multidisciplinary context. The consistent use of terms, definitions, and their multilingual equivalents ensures the accuracy of research, policymaking, and health communication.

To guarantee quality in terminology work, a structured validation process is necessary. This approach facilitates the creation of precise yet accessible definitions, aiming not only to support expert understanding across different cultural backgrounds, but also to make specialized knowledge more accessible to non-experts. In doing so, it contributes to the promotion of citizen science and the broader dissemination of scientific information across society.³

The process begins with compiling a corpus based on predefined parameters that consider the communication setting, including participants, medium, purpose, genre, location and time (Costa et al., 2024).

Next, candidate terms are identified through corpus analysis. This process enables terminologists to become familiar with domain-specific concepts and to recognize relevant variants, such as “gut-brain axis” and “brain-gut axis.” However, this analysis may also reveal quasi-synonyms or distinct concepts. In these latter two cases, it means there are two distinct terms representing two separate concepts, rather than one term with several variants representing a single concept. To address these distinctions, expert engagement is needed, bringing in specialists with deep knowledge and experience to actively contribute to discussions and decision-making. Their role is fundamental in validating terms, concepts, and definitions.

Finally, the concept is defined and integrated into a structured concept system. This includes establishing relations to broader and narrower terms, identifying synonyms, and validating the entry with domain experts. The process is iterative: expert feedback and corpus reanalysis are used to refine the definition and ensure alignment with current scientific understanding and terminology standards.

By grounding terminology in both linguistic evidence and expert consensus (Costa, 2013), this approach supports the development of reliable terminology resources, vital for policy coherence, scientific communication, and multilingual harmonization.

³ Within the present project, this process is necessarily iterative: expert feedback and non-expert feedback are integrated to assess the clarity and usability of simplified definitions, as stated in Section 5.

4 Stakeholders' Typology

In order to effectively validate terminology within the HEREDITARY project, it is important to recognize and differentiate the various stakeholders involved. Different stakeholders bring distinct perspectives, levels of expertise, and priorities, which can significantly shape the process needed to establish clear and consistent terminology.

To guide and structure the validation process, we apply a stakeholders' typology that categorizes participants according to their relationship with and use of medical terminology.

This typology will enable us to:

- i. Identify who should be consulted and involved at each stage.
- ii. Tailor communication and validation strategies to stakeholder expertise.
- iii. Balance technical accuracy and domain relevance with broader communicative needs.

The typology adopted for this project includes the following key stakeholder categories:

- a. **Medical Experts (Professional Users).** These are individuals with specialized knowledge and routine use of medical terminology, such as clinicians, biomedical researchers, and healthcare professors and professionals. Their input ensures that terms are medically accurate and aligned with current professional standards and practices.
- b. **Non-Expert or Incidental End Users.** This group includes patients, caregivers, administrative staff, policy experts, and laypeople. While they are not the primary users, their understanding of terms can significantly affect communication and decision-making. Their perspective is essential to identify ambiguous, overly technical, and inaccessible terminology.

The following sections will describe in greater detail the stakeholders identified.

4.1 Experts

- i. **Clinicians (physicians, nurses and other health professionals):** Clinicians are highly skilled health workers. Together with nurses and other health professionals, they “utilize a recognized scientific knowledge base and have the authority to direct the delivery of personal health services to a patient” (Institute of Medicine (US), 1994).
- ii. **Health researchers (biotechnologists, health data researchers):** Health researchers are individuals who carry out academic or scientific research in fields related to health and health data.

4.2 Non-Experts

- i. **Patients or patients' association representatives:** Patients are individuals who receive medical care or treatment from healthcare professionals due to illness, injury, or other health-related issues. Patients' associations are organizations formed to support and advocate for individuals affected by specific medical conditions.

- ii. **Caregivers:** A caregiver is someone who takes care of a person who is ill or disabled either as a family member or friend, or as a job.
- iii. **Health institution administrators:** Health institution administrators are professionals responsible for managing the operations of healthcare facilities such as hospitals and clinics.
- iv. **Policy-experts:** Policy-experts can be local government members, municipal or ministry representatives, social workers, etc.
- v. **Laypeople:** Laypeople are individuals who are not part of an association or a specific profession or specialty, and they do not have specialized knowledge or expertise in a particular area. They are ordinary citizens and members of the public who are not professionals or experts.

By distinguishing between expert and non-expert users of medical terminology, this typology supports a context and expertise-sensitive validation process, ensuring that terminology serves both professional precision and communicative clarity.

5 Workflow Description

The workflow for validating both specialized and simplified definitions is organized into several steps, some of which are further divided into specific tasks, as outlined below. Among these, Step 6 plays a particularly important role, as it includes the implementation of a survey (see Annex 1) and a subsequent questionnaire (see Section 7), which serves to assess the comprehensibility of the definitions among lay participants and to incorporate their feedback into the overall validation process.

Step 1: Selection of relevant terms for the collaborative dynamic component

To support the development of the collaborative dynamic component, relevant terms are carefully selected from the WP3 medical terminology database. This ensures consistency and accuracy in the use of domain-specific vocabulary throughout the project.

Step 2: Systematic identification of knowledge-rich contexts

In this phase, we will carry out the following actions using the terms identified through the methodology applied in Step 1:

- i. Conduct a comprehensive search for knowledge-rich contexts (KRC)⁴.
- ii. Identify and extract specialized textual definitions contained in the corpus⁵.
- iii. Cross-check the extracted data with terminological resources (TR).

The results will be analyzed to identify suitable contextual specialized definitions, which will be revised as necessary before submission to experts for validation.

Step 3: Validation of specialized definitions

⁴ "By knowledge-rich context, we designate a context indicating at least one item of domain knowledge that could be useful for conceptual analysis. In other words, the context should indicate at least one conceptual characteristic, whether it be an attribute or a relation." (Meyer, 2001, p.281).

⁵ The method used to compile the corpus is described in the deliverable D3.4 for Task 3.3 of WP3 (Costa et al, 2024).

Experts and clinicians will thoroughly evaluate the specialized definitions, assessing and rating them based on clarity and accuracy. To ensure consistency and reduce variability in interpretation, comprehensive guidelines will be provided to all experts prior to the evaluation process.

Step 4: Writing of simplified definitions

Based on the validated results from Steps 2 and 3, terminologists will proceed to draft simplified definitions. These definitions are intended to clearly and accurately convey the concept in a language that is accessible to non-expert audiences, thereby enhancing comprehension and usability across diverse user groups. The simplified definitions will be carefully reviewed to ensure they maintain the essential technical accuracy while improving clarity.

Step 5: Validation of simplified definitions by experts

Experts and clinicians will carefully review the simplified definitions, assessing and scoring them based on their clarity, accuracy, and overall effectiveness in conveying the intended meaning.

Step 6: Validation of simplified definitions via non-expert feedback

Non-experts will provide feedback on the simplified definitions previously reviewed by experts, as stated in Step 5. The aim is to assess whether non-experts understand the defined concepts. To implement this step, non-expert participants will complete a questionnaire designed to assess their comprehension of medical terminology, as outlined in Section 7. This questionnaire builds upon the exploratory survey described in Section 6, which serves as a preliminary step toward developing tools to improve access to and understanding of health information. Clear and comprehensive guidelines will be provided to non-experts to make the task as straightforward as possible, while ensuring they feel comfortable, even if they do not fully understand a definition or are unsure how to respond.

Step 7: Reformulation of the simplified definitions by terminologists

In this step, the simplified definitions written by the terminologists in Step 4 are critically reviewed. The primary goal is to ensure that feedback, both from experts and non-experts, has been thoroughly considered. This includes addressing potential ambiguities, redundancies, and inconsistencies, and making the necessary adjustments to enhance clarity and readability.

At this stage, input from subject matter experts and target users is incorporated to ensure the definitions are appropriately adapted to the needs of their intended audience.

Step 8: Validation of the reformulated simplified definitions by experts and non-experts

In this final step, experts and non-experts are expected to validate and confirm the accuracy of the rewritten simplified definitions. If any definitions require further improvement, Steps 7 and 8 will be revisited iteratively until all involved parties consider the definitions satisfactory.

Step 9: Feeding FAIRterm⁶

Ultimately, Step 9 finalizes the simplified definitions, preparing them for integration into the FAIRterm database.

⁶ See Section 8 of Deliverable 3.4: Medical terminology (<https://zenodo.org/records/14628022>)

Figure 1 Workflow description.

6 Methodology Used for the Design of the Survey

6.1 Introduction

The survey developed under Work Package 6 (WP6) of the HEREDITARY project – Health Literacy and Access to Health Information: A Socio-Demographic Survey (see Annex 1) – is an initial step toward designing a more detailed questionnaire that will allow us to develop tools for health information access and comprehension. This exploratory survey aims to understand knowledge, perceptions, and experiences surrounding health literacy, particularly focusing on how health-related information is accessed, understood, appraised and used by patients and caregivers, as well as conveyed by health experts. The results will contribute to the above-mentioned questionnaire, as well as to future interventions that enhance patient understanding and engagement with their own therapeutic process. Eligible participants are patients, caregivers, health professionals, health associate professionals, personal care workers in health services and health management and support personnel⁷ (see Section 4) aged 20 or older⁸. An informed consent form will be provided, informing participants that their contribution is voluntary and that all the information will be kept confidential.

6.2 Survey Structure

The survey is structured into two sections (see Annex 1): (1) Socio-demographic Information and (2) Health Literacy and Access to Health Information. This organization mirrors the recommendations found in health literacy survey frameworks, particularly the European Health Literacy Survey Questionnaire (HLS-EU-Q) (Pelikan et al., 2019), and ensures a logical flow from background information to specific health literacy behaviors and digital engagement. The selection and ordering of questions aim to minimize cognitive load on participants, beginning with general demographic questions before advancing towards more specific health-related inquiries, an approach recommended to enhance respondent engagement and data quality (Holtom et al., 2022). This structure also allows a comprehensive understanding of how demographic factors influence health literacy and information-seeking behavior.

6.3 Question Types and Justification

The survey predominantly applies closed-ended questions, including multiple-choice items and dichotomous (yes/no) questions. The use of closed formats is recommended to enhance reliability, facilitate standardized data analysis and reduce ambiguity in interpretation (Saris & Gallhofer, 2014).

In questions regarding preferences or behaviors (e.g., sources of health information), multiple-response options are included to better reflect the multifaceted nature of information-seeking in contemporary health contexts. The phrasing of questions

⁷ The participation of different health workers is based on the **international standard classification** presented by the World Health Organization (Health Workforce – WHO Team, 2019).

⁸ WHO defines 'Adolescents' as individuals in the 10-19 years age group (WHO, 2025a). This survey is aimed at participants from the age of 20 and over. According to WHO, Young Adulthood starts at age 20 (2025a).

prioritizes simplicity and neutrality to minimize bias and maximize comprehension, particularly important when addressing populations with varying literacy levels.

6.4 Sections Overview

Section I focuses on socio-demographic information, gathering data on several key background variables such as age (using five-year intervals)⁹, gender identity (offering inclusive options beyond binary categories), educational attainment aligned with ISCED 2011 classifications (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2012), place of residence, socio-economic status, and professional background. These variables enable analysis of how social determinants relate to health literacy outcomes.

Section II assesses participants' behaviors and self-perceptions regarding the reading, understanding, and seeking of health information. Given the variety of medical document types, we will provide stakeholders with a predefined typology (Annex 2). The ease with which individuals can access healthcare, a fundamental factor in health literacy, is also considered. The question design in this section drew heavily from the European Health Literacy Survey (European Health Information Portal, 2025) and similar health literacy tools. It also explores the role of digital technologies in accessing health-related information, reflecting the increasing relevance of eHealth literacy in citizen science projects (Prinzellner et al., 2022).

6.5 Ethical Considerations

Participation in the survey is entirely voluntary, with no personally identifiable information collected. In fact, participants will be asked to create their own Unique Code (SGIC)¹⁰, by creating a code based on simple, memorable (but non-identifying) details. Table 1 presents the instructions participants will be given before answering the survey:

⁹ The age band presented in this study is based on the Age Group Code list presented by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2025b).

¹⁰ “Self-generated identification codes (SGICs) are strings of information based on stable participants’ characteristics. They are often used in longitudinal research to match data between time points while protecting participant anonymity”. (Little, et. al., 2021, p. 354).

Table 1 Creating a Self-Generated Identification Code (SGIC).

Your Participant Code (SGIC)	
<u>You will use this same code for future questionnaires</u>	
To help us anonymously link your responses across different questionnaires, please create a personal code using the following format:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The first two letters of the city where you were born• The last digit of your birth year• The last two letters of your favourite animal• The digit that corresponds to the number of your siblings	
E.g.: If you were born in Copenhagen in 1986, if your favourite animal is a panda and if you don't have any siblings, your code is: CO6DA0	
Please <u>write this code down</u> and save it!	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Your Code: [_____]	

This method helps preserve anonymity while enabling repeat matching. Likewise, the survey includes a statement assuring participants of the ethical handling of their data (see Annex 1). This statement was written considering the guidelines presented in WHO's Research Ethics Review Committee (ERC) (WHO, 2025c) and in ICPSR - Recommended Informed Consent Language for Data Sharing (ICPSR, 2025).

Sensitive questions, such as those regarding income, include "prefer not to answer" options to ensure participants maintain control over their disclosures, in line with ethical guidelines for socio-economic research presented in the OECD Global Science Forum report (OECD, 2016).

6.6 Limitations

Given its exploratory nature, the survey employs a non-random sample, which may limit generalizability. Even so, this initial survey represents an essential step in establishing foundational understanding, from which more robust and targeted tools can be developed. Online distribution may also exclude individuals with limited digital literacy or internet access — this is why in-person distribution will also be considered, to prevent barriers to full participation.

6.7 Conclusion

This survey provides a robust framework for assessing health literacy and access to health information. By combining socio-demographic data with insights into health information practices, this methodology allows for a comprehensive analysis of the factors influencing health literacy. The findings from this survey can inform interventions and strategies to improve health communication and promote health literacy within the population.

7 Methodology Used for the Design of the Questionnaire Script

7.1 Introduction

This questionnaire will be the main instrument for assessing the comprehension of medical terminology (see Costa et al. 2024) among non-experts (see Section 4.2). Building on the preliminary results collected through the socio-demographic and health literacy survey, it adopts an experimental methodology to assess how different definitions of medical terms (specialized versus simplified) affect understanding of key health concepts. The instrument is designed to examine the relationship between perceived familiarity and comprehension of selected terms and the extent to which simplified definitions improve conceptual understanding. The data collected will contribute to the validation and refinement of accessible medical terminological resources, supporting the simplification of complex language for a wide range of stakeholders and end users.

7.2 Objectives

The overall objective of this questionnaire is to assess participants' familiarity with selected health-related terms and their understanding of the underlying concepts when presented with definitions at varying levels of simplification, thereby contributing to the validation of simplified definitions (as described in Step 6 of the Workflow description, in Section 5).

Specifically, the instrument is designed to evaluate:

- The degree of familiarity participants report concerning a set of medical terms.
- Their ability to correctly interpret and understand the concepts designated by the selected terms.
- Whether the proposed simplified definitions contribute to improved conceptual comprehension compared to specialized definitions.

The findings will directly inform future interventions aimed at enhancing the intelligibility and accessibility of healthcare communication and biomedical terminology resources.

7.3 Selection of Corpora for Terminological Data

7.3.1 Selection of Terms and Definitions

The questionnaire addresses a set of terms selected through the terminological data extraction carried out in Work Package 3 (WP3), identified not only in specialized texts but also in commonly used patient communication, based on the semi-specialized corpus compiled for the project (see Section 7.3.2). For each selected term, we will extract definitional elements and/or specialized definitions to propose simplified definitions adapted for non-experts (see Section 3.3).

Each participant is presented with only one of the two definitions for each term. The use of alternative definitions (simplified and specialized) allows for the comparison of comprehension outcomes with respect to the degree of technicality.

7.3.2 Overview of Corpora and Creation of a Corpus of Semi-Specialized texts

For the purposes of this analysis, two distinct corpora will be used: one composed of specialized texts, already described in the deliverable D3.4 for Task 3.3 of WP3 (Costa et al, 2024), and a second corpus consisting of semi-specialized texts.

The creation of a corpus of semi-specialized texts constitutes a fundamental step within the framework of the present analysis. In particular, these texts are written with the aim of ensuring that medical information is accessible to patients and lay users, prioritizing both clarity and understanding. The goal is to identify the medical terms used in the collected texts, with the purpose of assessing whether terms are comprehensible to users, with special reference to the patients targeted by the HEREDITARY project. In addition, having access to both a semi-specialized and a specialized corpus allows for: 1) a comparative analysis of the corpora, and 2) the comparative assessment of term comprehensibility for patients and lay users, by evaluating the understandability of terms found in semi-specialized texts alongside terms used in specialized texts only.

The examination of domain-specific texts aimed at patients and the general public, indeed, enables one to observe how specialized medical information is specifically conveyed to non-expert audiences. A comparative analysis of the specialized and semi-specialized corpora is essential for identifying the medical terms used by healthcare professionals in expert-to-expert communication, as opposed to the terms used by domain experts when addressing patients and lay audiences. The insights gained from this analysis will support an in-depth examination of medical terminology that additionally considers the diastatic variation of language, thus reflecting differences in usage across social groups.

The corpus of semi-specialized texts will comprise documents written in the following six languages: English, French, German, Italian, Portuguese and Spanish. Articles originally written in these languages will be included in the corpus, while translated texts will be excluded. For each language under analysis, a list of sources of semi-specialized texts is provided below. Moreover, links to texts from these sources are provided (Annex 3), to offer an overview of representative texts that could constitute part of the corpus.

7.3.2.1 English Language

i. **MSD Manual Consumer Version.** The MSD Manual contains articles intended for both domain experts and non-experts. To address these distinct users, the website features two dedicated sections: the MSD Manual Professional Version, which includes scientific articles aimed at medical professionals, and the MSD Manual Consumer Version, which is tailored to lay users. Only documents from the Consumer Version are included within the corpus.

ii. **MedlinePlus.** It is a health information platform designed for patients, families and caregivers. It is provided by the National Library of Medicine (NLM), which is the world's largest medical library and part of the National Institutes of Health (NIH).

iii. National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke website. This website features distinct sections, respectively tailored to researchers, patients and caregivers, and health professionals.

7.3.2.2 French Language

i. Santé publique France website. Santé publique France is the national public health agency of France. The website features a wide range of contents, including materials that are easily accessible and understandable to non-experts.

ii. ameli.fr website. It is the official website of the French health insurance system (l'Assurance Maladie). The site includes a section dedicated to insured individuals and another for healthcare professionals. The texts specifically aimed at insured people are written in language that is easy to understand.

iii. Inserm website. It is the official website of the Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale. The website includes an "Information en santé" section, which provides content for two distinct audiences: "Pour tout public" and "Pour public avancé". The texts are taken from the "Pour tout public" section (see Annex 3).

iv. Vidal website. It is a knowledge database, updated by medical experts among which pharmacists, physicians and specialists in clinical pharmacology and therapeutics. It is approved by the Haute Autorité de Santé (HAS).

7.3.2.3 German Language

i. Gesundheitsinformation.de website. It is a website operated by the IQWiG (Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlichkeit im Gesundheitswesen), commissioned by the Federal Ministry of Health. It contains texts written and reviewed by medical experts and its aim is to enhance patient understanding of medical information.

ii. Apotheken Umschau website. As declared on the website, the content is reviewed by a scientific editorial team formed by physicians and pharmacists. The declared aim of the website is to provide content that is easy to understand.

iii. NetDoktor website. It is a health information website, developed in collaboration with medical experts and professional journalists, providing content on medical topics.

7.3.2.4 Italian Language

i. ISSalute website. This platform, developed by the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), is specifically designed to provide medical information using clear and accessible language.

ii. Fondazione Veronesi Magazine. This is an online platform curated by the Fondazione Umberto Veronesi, that is a leading foundation dedicated to promoting and disseminating health information.

7.3.2.5 Portuguese Language

i. Cuf website. It is the official website of a Portuguese healthcare provider, featuring a section titled "Saúde A-Z" that provides health-related information for the general public. The content is conveyed in clear and accessible language, aiming to clarify symptoms, causes, and treatment options for various conditions.

- ii. Atlas da Saúde. It is a Portuguese health communication platform that publishes articles and news intended for non-specialists. The content is written in non-technical language, aiming to raise public awareness about diseases, treatments, and advancements in healthcare science.
- iii. Multicare Website. It is the website of a health insurance provider in Portugal. It features a blog that provides clear and accessible information on various health topics, including neurodegenerative diseases. The content is designed for patients and caregivers, aiming to increase awareness and understanding of various conditions.
- iv. Lusíadas website. It is the website of a Portuguese healthcare provider offering information on various diseases, including clear explanations of symptoms, diagnoses, and treatments. The content is designed for a non-specialist audience.
- v. Medicare website. Medicare is a Portuguese private healthcare and insurance company. Its website includes a section titled “Mais Saúde”, which provides health information aimed at the general public. The language used is simple and informative, covering diseases and health promotion.

7.3.2.6 Spanish Language

- i. GuíaSalud website. It is the official website of GuíaSalud, which is an agency of the Spanish National Health System. The website includes a dedicated section with information specifically designed for patients.
- ii. Clínica Universidad de Navarra website. It is the official website of the Clínica Universidad de Navarra, which provides content that is adapted to a non-expert audience.

7.4 Participant Assignment

To rigorously evaluate the effect of simplified definitions on comprehension, the questionnaire will follow a between-subjects experimental design, dividing participants into two groups:

- Group A receives the version of the questionnaire with specialized definitions.
- Group B receives the version of the questionnaire with simplified definitions.

Both groups answer the same questions on familiarity and comprehension, allowing for a direct comparison of conceptual understanding between the two groups exposed to different definitions. This method minimizes bias from exposure to multiple definitions and supports the controlled assessment and validation of the simplified definitions proposed.

7.5 Questionnaire Script

Both versions of the questionnaire (A and B) consist of replicated blocks of questions (one per term), structured as follows:

[TERM]

a. Familiarity Assessment

Participants will be asked to self-report their familiarity with the medical term using a 5-point Likert scale:

Question: "How familiar are you with the term [TERM]?"

Scale:

1 - Not at All Familiar

2 - Slightly Familiar

3 - Somewhat Familiar

4 - Moderately Familiar

5 - Extremely Familiar

b. Comprehension Check

In this section, Group A respondents are presented with a specialized definition and Group B respondents are presented with a simplified definition. Subsequently, both groups answer the same comprehension question. This question may take the form of a true or false, multiple-choice, or short-answer question, and is designed to assess the participant's understanding of the concept after reading its definition.

c. Open-ended Response

Participants are asked to explain the concept in their own words to gather qualitative insights into their interpretation of the concept and potential misconceptions.

This structure aims to balance cognitive load and encourage engagement, supporting quantitative and qualitative analyses.

7.6 Data Analysis

The analysis of the results includes both quantitative and qualitative features.

7.6.1 Quantitative Analysis

i. Familiarity–Comprehension Correlation

Statistical analysis will examine the correlation between the self-reported familiarity of the participants with the selected medical terms and their actual comprehension of the underlying concepts. This analysis provides insights into the predictive validity of perceived knowledge.

ii. Comparison of Comprehension Scores by Definition Type

The percentage of correct responses to the comprehension questions will be calculated for Group A and Group B. Comparing these accuracy rates allows for the evaluation of the relative effectiveness of each type of definition, determining whether simplified definitions for the pre-selected terms consistently result in improved understanding.

7.6.2 Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative data will be analyzed in order to identify patterns of interpretation, recurring misunderstandings, and the discursive and terminological features that facilitate comprehension. In particular, the analysis will seek to:

- i. Analyze open-ended responses in order to identify patterns of misunderstanding and interpretation.
- ii. Assess whether simplified definitions lead to clearer or more accurate explanations, by participants, of the concepts defined.

7.7 Practical Relevance and Future Application

The data collected through this questionnaire will enhance our understanding of the effect of varying degrees of specialization in definitions and its impact on comprehension in health-related contexts. It is meant to inform the development of terminological resources and communication materials. The findings will help:

- i. Identify terms and concepts that present particular challenges for non-experts.
- ii. Evaluate the extent to which simplified definitions enhance conceptual understanding.
- iii. Support the development of strategies and terminological tools that simplify scientific language and enhance accessibility in healthcare.

Ultimately, the results will support evidence-based recommendations for improving patient education, fostering health literacy, and enhancing the overall quality of communication between healthcare practitioners and non-experts.

8 Preparing Stakeholders Before Answering the Questionnaire

8.1 Introduction

Stakeholders' engagement in research production is being increasingly recognized in the health field as a crucial contribution to improving data design, ensuring data quality and making scientific outputs more responsive to society's needs (Boaz et al., 2018; Rix et al., 2020; Hall et al., 2024). To foster meaningful involvement, a strategy must be defined on how to involve stakeholders and prepare them to participate effectively.

8.2 Adapting Communication to Support Informed Participation

Considering the stakeholder typology described in Section 4, questionnaires follow a stakeholder-centric approach, being adapted to the different literacy levels, and contexts. An introductory text is provided, presenting the HEREDITARY project and its goals, as well as an explanation of the purpose of the questionnaire. Visual aids, such as infographics, may be useful (Rix et al., 2020). This preparatory strategy promotes clarity, comprehension and motivates participation throughout the project (Elkins et al., 2011; Rüfenacht et al., 2021; Gulombic et al., 2024). Besides contact details for support, key ethical considerations (that is, information on informed consent procedures, data confidentiality and on how collected data will be used in the project outputs) are also provided. Ethical preparation is essential for public trust in health-related research (WHO, 2023). Communication channels may be face-to-face (in HSLs), online, or project channels, like the website, social media or newsletters.

8.3 Pilot Testing and Feedback Loops

Before formal distribution, a pilot version of the questionnaire will be shared with a sample of stakeholders, in order to test, refine and ensure this tool's robustness and reinforce the overall credibility of the research findings. Participants from both typology groups (experts and non-experts) will be asked to provide feedback and suggest improvements. Clarity, tone, length, and cultural appropriateness are some of the factors to be taken into account. This strategy is aligned with the best practices in inclusive citizen science recruitment and engagement (Sanz, 2020; Hidalgo et al. 2021).

8.4 Continuous Support and Follow-Up

Participants will have access to support contact throughout the process. As this project involves long-term participation, regular check-ins and brief updates on findings will be shared and discussed through the project's communication channels to ensure transparency and interaction. To address common concerns, a FAQ page will be created and updated. In addition, social media will be used to maintain ongoing communication and keep participants informed.

9 Future Work

The developed survey and questionnaire represent a fundamental initial step toward understanding how knowledge concerning health-related topics is accessed and used by patients and caregivers. These instruments also offer relevant insights into how medical information is conveyed to patients and caregivers by domain experts. Future interventions, however, should take into consideration potential comprehension issues related to the survey and questionnaire questions and answers, particularly those that may arise due to the advanced age of patients affected by neurodegenerative disorders. Indeed, it is essential to adapt the language used, considering that older patients and caregivers could experience some difficulties in understanding concepts designated by terms such as ‘app’, ‘internet search engines’ and ‘social media’, which appear in the survey.

Moreover, varying levels of health literacy do not represent the only factor to consider when developing patient-oriented materials. As a matter of fact, patients targeted by the HEREDITARY project may additionally experience different levels of cognitive decline. This variability is addressed in the terminology resource currently under development (WP3), which offers multiple explanations of medical concepts, each tailored to the cognitive needs of patients affected by a broad spectrum of neurodegenerative disorders (Bonato et al., 2025). A similar approach could be applied to the formulation of the survey and questionnaire questions and answers, as well as to the drafting of informed consent documents. Indeed, adapting these documents to the varying levels of cognitive decline among patients can maximize comprehension and ensure that the documents are more inclusive and patient oriented.

Additionally, future work should include translating the survey and questionnaire into multiple languages (such as French, German, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish) to ensure broader accessibility and cultural appropriateness in diverse contexts.

In parallel, a dissemination strategy will be developed to support the effective distribution of the survey and questionnaire among a broad and varied group of patients and caregivers, extending the reach and relevance of the instruments. Initially, the implementation will involve participants from the Health Social Labs, who will serve as a pilot group for preliminary testing of the instruments. Subsequently, broader dissemination will be pursued through a combination of strategies currently under consideration, e.g. distribution within healthcare institutions, via the HEREDITARY project website and social media channels, and through crowdsourcing platforms to reach a wider and more heterogeneous audience.

10 Conclusions

This report has underscored the critical importance of clear and accessible communication in the context of health research, particularly within citizen science initiatives across Europe. As public participation in health-related research grows, so does the responsibility to ensure that scientific terms, concepts, and procedures are communicated in a way that supports understanding, trust, and meaningful contribution.

The proposed approach, which combines validation by experts with comprehension-based validation of simplified definitions by non-experts, offers a practical framework for addressing this need. By actively involving non-experts in the assessment of terminology and placing terminologists at the core of the process, the method ensures both scientific accuracy and public accessibility. This is especially vital in health research, where miscommunication can lead to misunderstanding, disengagement, or even harm.

Terminologists play a pivotal role in mediating between expert language and lay understanding, ensuring that health-related terminology is not only technically correct but also ethically and culturally appropriate. Their collaboration with researchers and citizen participants enhances the quality, inclusivity, and impact of health research communication.

By adopting this methodology, health research projects can lead the way in promoting transparency, inclusivity, and public trust — key pillars of responsible and impactful research. This approach supports the EU's broader goals of open science and citizen engagement, ensuring that advances in health research are both scientifically robust and socially responsive.

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The bibliographic entries are arranged in lexicographical order based on the key, following the APA style. This enables us to place the entries and citations in the table and text in any sequence, allowing for later sorting while ensuring consistency.

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Annexes

Number	Title
Annex 1	Health Literacy and Access to Health Information: A Socio-Demographic Survey
Annex 2	Typology and Types of Medical Documents
Annex 3	Sources of Semi-Specialized Texts